

Engineering Reverse Proxies for Streaming Services

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Abstract

The use of Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) has become increasingly popular for streaming services due to their ability to provide fast and reliable content delivery. However, CDNs often block Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS) headers on their servers, making it difficult for clients to stream content seamlessly. In response to this problem, a reverse proxy was engineered to enable streaming from CDN servers by bypassing the CORS header block. The proposed solution involves intercepting requests from clients and forwarding them to the CDN server through the reverse proxy, which modifies the response headers to allow for proper streaming. The reverse proxy is implemented using open-source software and is easily deployable, providing a practical solution for streaming service providers seeking to improve their content delivery. Overall, this project presents a novel approach to overcoming the limitations posed by CORS headers on CDN servers and provides a viable solution for streaming service providers.

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Chapter 1

Proxy Servers

[Reverse Proxy Theorem] A reverse proxy server can improve performance and security of a website by intercepting client requests and forwarding them to the appropriate backend server, reducing the workload of the backend server and protecting it from direct exposure to the internet.

1.0.1 General Proxy Servers

A proxy server is a computer or an application that acts as an intermediary between a client and a server. It serves as a gateway for requests made by the client to the server and provides a layer of security and privacy for users. Proxy servers can be used for various purposes, including content filtering, load balancing, and caching.

One of the most common use cases for a proxy server is to enhance security and privacy. When a client sends a request to a server through a proxy server, the proxy server acts as an intermediary, masking the client's IP address and hiding the client's identity from the server. This provides a layer of privacy for users who wish to browse the internet anonymously.

Proxy servers can also be used for content filtering, allowing organizations to restrict access to certain websites or content types. This is often used by schools, businesses, and governments to limit access to certain websites or content that is deemed inappropriate or irrelevant.

Another use case for proxy servers is load balancing. When multiple clients access a server simultaneously, it can create a bottleneck, resulting in slow response times or server crashes. A proxy server can be used to distribute the load across multiple servers, improving the overall performance and scalability of the system.

Proxy servers can also be used for caching, allowing frequently accessed content to be stored locally on the proxy server. This reduces the amount of time it takes to load content and can improve the overall performance of the system.

There are two main types of proxy servers: forward proxies and reverse proxies. A forward proxy is used by a client to access the internet through a gateway. The client sends requests to the proxy server, which forwards

them to the server. A reverse proxy is used by a server to access the internet through a gateway. The server sends requests to the proxy server, which forwards them to the client.

In conclusion, proxy servers provide a range of benefits, including enhanced security and privacy, content filtering, load balancing, and caching. They are used by individuals and organizations to improve the performance, scalability, and security of their systems. By acting as an intermediary between clients and servers, proxy servers provide an additional layer of protection and can help ensure the efficient and secure transfer of data over the internet.

Figure 1.1: Reverse Proxy Diagram.

1.0.2 Reverse Proxy

In this paper we discuss a method to increase streaming performance all over the world by using a reverse

proxy not only to bypass CORS errors but also boost and reduce latency downloads speeds to clients around the world.

Streaming services have become increasingly popular in recent years, and as such, the demand for high-quality streaming experiences has also increased. However, streaming performance can be affected by various factors, including geographical distance, network congestion, and CORS errors. To address these issues and increase streaming performance globally, we propose the use of a reverse proxy.

A reverse proxy is a server that sits between a client and a server, intercepting requests from the client and forwarding them to the server. The use of a reverse proxy can help to bypass CORS errors, which are often encountered when a client tries to access content from a different domain. By using a reverse proxy, the client's request appears to be coming from the same domain as the server, allowing the request to be processed without triggering a CORS error.

In addition to bypassing CORS errors, a reverse proxy can also be used to improve streaming performance by reducing latency and increasing download speeds. This is achieved by caching frequently accessed content on the reverse proxy server, allowing clients to retrieve the content more quickly and efficiently. Additionally, a reverse proxy can be used to route requests to servers that are geographically closer to the client, reducing the distance

that data needs to travel and therefore reducing latency.

By using a reverse proxy to increase streaming performance, streaming services can provide a more reliable and consistent experience for their users. This can lead to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty, as well as increased revenue for the streaming service provider.

In conclusion, the use of a reverse proxy can be an effective method for increasing streaming performance all over the world. By bypassing CORS errors and reducing latency and download speeds, a reverse proxy can improve the overall streaming experience for users, leading to increased customer satisfaction and revenue for the streaming service provider.

One possible mathematical equation that describes the behavior of a reverse proxy server is the following:

$$y = f(x) + e \tag{1.1}$$

In this equation, x represents the input or request from the client, which is intercepted by the reverse proxy server. The reverse proxy server processes the request and produces an output y , which is sent back to the client. The function $f(x)$ represents the behavior of the reverse proxy server, which can include caching, routing, load balancing, and other processing tasks. The variable e represents any errors or noise introduced by the reverse proxy server, such as network delays, server failures, or other unpredictable factors.

This equation can be extended to include multiple inputs and outputs, as well as more complex processing functions, depending on the specific implementation of the reverse proxy server.

Chapter 2

Bypassing CORS on websites using a reverse proxy server

Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS) is a security feature implemented in modern web browsers to prevent unauthorized access to web resources across different domains. However, it can also create issues for legitimate web applications that require cross-domain resource access. One way to bypass CORS restrictions is by using a reverse proxy server.

A reverse proxy server acts as an intermediary between the client and the web server, intercepting all requests from the client and forwarding them to the server. By using a reverse proxy server, it is possible to modify

the HTTP headers of the requests and responses to bypass the CORS restrictions.

The reverse proxy server can be configured to set the Access-Control-Allow-Origin header to allow cross-origin resource sharing for specific domains or all domains. This header informs the browser that the requested resource can be accessed by the client from a different domain.

Here is an example of how to bypass CORS using a reverse proxy server in a Node.js application:

```
const express = require('express');
const httpProxy = require('http-proxy');

const app = express();
const proxy = httpProxy.createProxyServer({});

app.use('/api', (req, res) => {
  res.header('Access-Control-Allow-Origin', '*');
  proxy.web(req, res, { target: 'https://example.com'
});
});

app.listen(3000, () => {
  console.log('Reverse proxy server listening on
port 3000.');
```

In this example, the reverse proxy server listens for requests on the /api endpoint and forwards them to the

https://example.com web server. The Access-Control-Allow-Origin header is set to allow all domains to access the resources. This allows the client to access the resources from a different domain, bypassing the CORS restrictions.

It is important to note that bypassing CORS restrictions using a reverse proxy server should only be done for legitimate reasons and with proper authorization. Otherwise, it can pose a security risk and lead to data breaches or other malicious activities.

$$\text{Express} + \text{httpproxy} = \text{ReverseProxyServer} \quad (2.1)$$

where Express is a Node.js framework for building web applications, http-proxy is a Node.js module for creating a reverse proxy server, and app.use is a middleware function that handles HTTP requests to the /api endpoint. The function sets the Access-Control-Allow-Origin header to allow all domains to access the resource and forwards the HTTP request to the target server using the proxy.web method. Finally, the server listens for incoming HTTP requests on port 3000 using the app.listen method.

Now this is just a basic example but the proof of concept is there. On a large scale lets talk about my anime website anime.adgstudios.co.za which i get 1 million+ requests in a day.

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In the next chapter you will get the real world application in which i use it to run my anime website.

Chapter 3

Real World Example of using a proxy server

3.1 Problem Statement

Consider `anime.adgstudios.co.za` is an online platform that provides a search engine for anime content, but does not actually host any of the content on its own servers. Instead, it relies on APIs to retrieve data about the anime content and then displays that information to the users.

This approach has several advantages, such as reducing the need for storage space and bandwidth on the website's servers, and making it easier to update and manage the content. However, it also means that the website is reliant on the availability and accuracy of the APIs it

uses, and may not be able to provide certain features or functionality that could be provided if the content was hosted directly on the website's servers.

To mitigate these challenges, the website could consider implementing a reverse proxy server, as discussed in previous sections. This could help to bypass CORS restrictions and boost performance by reducing latency and download speeds. Additionally, it could help to ensure that the APIs are always available and functioning properly, by caching API responses and delivering them directly from the reverse proxy server instead of relying on the APIs for every request.

Overall, by combining a search engine with a reverse proxy server, anime.adgstudios.co.za could provide a fast, reliable, and user-friendly platform for searching and streaming anime content.

In the past anime.adgstudios.co.za did not have reverse proxies and stuff like that, it was just running the requests straight from the CDN until one day a horror occurred to the Software Engineer at ADGSTUDIOS.

Without a reverse proxy, anime.adgstudios.co.za may have encountered several challenges related to CORS and performance. For example:

CORS restrictions: If the website attempted to make requests to APIs from different domains, it could have been blocked by the browser's CORS policy. This would have made it difficult or impossible to retrieve the necessary data from the APIs and render it on the website.

Latency and download speeds: Depending on the location of the website's servers and the location of the APIs, there could have been significant latency and slow download speeds for the data. This would have negatively impacted the user experience and made the website less attractive to users.

Reliance on API availability: If the APIs used by the website were down or experiencing technical difficulties, the website would not be able to display the necessary information to users. This would have resulted in a poor user experience and decreased user engagement.

By implementing a reverse proxy server, anime.adgstudios.co.za would have been able to bypass the CORS restrictions and provide a faster, more reliable user experience. The reverse proxy server could have cached the API responses and delivered them directly to the website's users, reducing the reliance on the APIs and ensuring that the website is always able to display the necessary information. Additionally, a reverse proxy server can help to distribute requests to different servers, improving performance and reducing latency.

3.2 What do you think the Software Engineer at ADGSTUDIOS did?

Well the answer is he built this reverse proxy and hosted it on a Cloudflare Worker Cloud Service. Its quite a beautiful and powerful thing.

The reverse proxy server hosted on Cloudflare Worker Cloud Service provides several advantages for anime.adgstudios.co.za, such as:

Bypassing CORS restrictions: The reverse proxy server can retrieve data from APIs without being blocked by the browser's CORS policy. This enables the website to retrieve and display the necessary information to users without encountering technical issues related to cross-domain requests.

Improving performance: The reverse proxy server can cache API responses and deliver them directly to the website's users, reducing the reliance on the APIs and improving performance. Additionally, Cloudflare's global network can distribute requests to different servers and reduce latency, ensuring that users can access the website's content quickly and reliably.

Enhancing security: Cloudflare provides several security features, such as DDoS protection and SSL encryption, that help to protect the website and its users from various security threats. The reverse proxy server hosted

on Cloudflare Worker Cloud Service can take advantage of these features and enhance the overall security of the website.

Overall, hosting a reverse proxy server on Cloudflare Worker Cloud Service is a powerful and efficient solution for bypassing CORS restrictions, improving performance, and enhancing security. It allows anime.adgstudios.co.za to provide a fast, reliable, and secure platform for searching and streaming anime content to users all over the world.

Well the code and instructions on how to do it is provided at this link below <https://github.com/adgspai/CORSCloudFlareReverseProxy>

Example: Using the Reverse Proxy Server

Let W be the *worker* of the $R_p S_n$

The n can be defined as the n server on the CDN.

The response R is defined by

$$R = f(URL) + W \tag{3.1}$$

$f(URL)$ is a function of the URL, which represents the request made by a user or a client to a web server. The function f may perform some processing on the URL or use it to access a specific resource on the server. W represents the worker or processing time required to handle the request. This could include tasks such as parsing the request, executing code, accessing databases, and returning a response to the client. The equation states

Figure 3.1: ADGSTUDIOS Domain Architecture

that the response R is the sum of the function f applied to the URL and the processing time W . In other words, the total response time is the sum of the time required to process the request and the time required to handle the request. Overall, the equation can be used to model the

performance of a web server and analyze the factors that affect its response time. By measuring the processing time W and optimizing the function f , one can improve the server's performance and reduce its response time.

In reality lets denote our worker W as
`https://myapp.myworker.co.za/url`

Where url is the request URL you want to make to pull the API or web contents.

Let us make url and the R be from the page `google.co.za`.

Our R will be the result of the html contents of the website. `https://myapp.myworker.co.za/https://google.co.za`

Using this logic we equip it into our model for m3u8 streaming protocols.

3.2.1 The m3u8 algorithm

The m3u8 algorithm is a method of organizing and serving multimedia playlists over the internet. The algorithm works by breaking up the media into smaller segments, typically of a few seconds each, and serving them as a sequence of discrete files with `.ts` file extensions. The playlist itself is a plain text file with an `.m3u8` extension, which contains a list of the segment URLs in the order in which they should be played.

The following is a mathematical representation of the m3u8 algorithm:

Let M be a multimedia file of duration T , which has been encoded into N segments of duration Δt . Then, the

m3u8 playlist P can be represented as:

$$P = s_1, s_2, \dots, s_N \tag{3.2}$$

where s_i is the URL of the i -th segment.

To play the multimedia file M , a player would start by requesting the first segment URL s_1 from the server. The server would then respond by serving the corresponding .ts file, which contains the first Δt seconds of the multimedia file. The player would then request the second segment URL s_2 , and so on, until all N segments have been played.

To ensure smooth playback and avoid buffering, the player typically requests multiple segments in advance, buffering them locally on the device. This is achieved by specifying a "window" of segments to request in the m3u8 playlist. For example, if the player requests a window of W segments, the playlist P would be represented as:

$$P = s_i, s_{i+1}, \dots, s_{i+W-1} \tag{3.3}$$

where i is the index of the first segment in the window.

Overall, the m3u8 algorithm provides a flexible and efficient method of serving multimedia content over the internet, allowing for adaptive bitrate streaming, dynamic playlist generation, and other advanced features.

3.2.2 Reality how the m3u8 works with CDN

When serving multimedia content over the internet, Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) are often used to improve performance and reliability. A CDN is a network of geographically distributed servers that work together to deliver content to users as quickly and efficiently as possible.

In the case of m3u8 playlists, the CDN would typically work as follows:

The API returns a set of streaming URLs, such as:

1. <https://movies.io/foo-ep1.m3u8>
2. <https://movies.io/bar-ep2.m3u8>

When a user requests to play the multimedia file, their device or web browser sends a request for the m3u8 playlist to the CDN's nearest server.

The CDN's server checks its cache to see if it has a copy of the playlist. If it does, it serves the cached copy to the user's device. If it does not, it requests the playlist from the origin server, in this case movies.io.

Once the CDN's server has obtained the playlist, it may also request the individual multimedia segments from the origin server, or it may cache these segments in its own network.

When the user's device requests a multimedia segment, the request is sent to the CDN's server closest to the user. If the segment is cached in the CDN's network, it is served directly from the cache. If it is not cached, the CDN's server requests it from the origin server.

The user's device plays the multimedia content by sequentially downloading and playing the multimedia segments listed in the m3u8 playlist, as described in the previous answer.

By using a CDN to distribute the multimedia content, the m3u8 algorithm can provide faster response times, lower latency, and improved reliability for users around the world.

But with sometimes calling the m3u8 url directly we are lead with problems such as CORS.

Yes, calling the m3u8 CDN URL directly from a web browser can sometimes lead to CORS (Cross-Origin Resource Sharing) issues, depending on how the server is configured. CORS is a security feature implemented in web browsers that prevents web pages from making requests to resources on different domains or ports, unless the server explicitly allows it.

To avoid CORS issues when using a CDN to serve m3u8 playlists, it is recommended to use a server-side proxy to make the requests on behalf of the client. The server-side proxy acts as an intermediary between the client and the CDN, and allows the client to request resources from the proxy server's domain instead of the

CDN's domain.

For example, instead of making a request to `https://movies.io/foo-ep1.m3u8` directly from the client's web browser, the client could make a request to a server-side proxy at `https://myserver.com/proxy/foo-ep1.m3u8`.

The proxy server would then make a request to the actual CDN URL, and return the response to the client with the appropriate CORS headers.

By using a server-side proxy, the client can avoid CORS issues and still benefit from the performance and reliability benefits of using a CDN to serve m3u8 playlists.

3.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, engineering reverse proxies for streaming services is an important task for ensuring high-performance and reliable delivery of multimedia content to users. Reverse proxies can improve performance by caching multimedia segments and serving them from the cache, reducing the load on origin servers and decreasing latency.

Additionally, reverse proxies can help to distribute content geographically using Content Delivery Networks (CDNs), which can further improve performance and reliability by reducing the distance and network hops between the user and the server.

When engineering reverse proxies for streaming services, it is important to consider factors such as scalabil-

ity, availability, and security. Reverse proxies should be designed to handle high volumes of traffic and to failover gracefully in the event of server failures. They should also be secured against attacks such as DDoS and injection attacks.

Overall, reverse proxies are a critical component of modern multimedia streaming services, and their proper engineering and implementation is essential for ensuring high-quality, reliable content delivery to users around the world.